

Predictive Analysis Shaping the Future of Online Business

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Marketing is no more limited to just reacting to your customers' behavior. You can now predict their behavior with advanced technology and initiatives. Predictive analytics is quickly becoming the hottest way to proactively market to consumers on the internet. Online businesses use historic data and outcomes to build predictive models that provide information on near-term and long-term customer behavior. It looks at what has happened to date, and applies statistical models to reliably forecast what will happen next. It sounds a little bit like magic, but it's actually just math. It lets you decide what a customer will do in the future based on the information you have about that entire population and what that individual has done before. You can then group people together based on these individual predictions to project what those segments of the population will do in future. This way, predictive analytics enables organizations to adapt more quickly to changing conditions, pinpoint how likely their strategies are to succeed in the future, and make decisions even in the absence of historical data.

Benefits of Predictive Modelling:

Historical analytics are critical for making sense of what's happened to date. But here are some advantages of incorporating predictive analytics into your business' decision-making framework, which can be defined as "The Triple A":

Agility: Historical analytics requires a certain amount of time to pass in order to derive meaningful conclusions, so it takes longer to see which strategies are beneficial and which are failing. Predictive analytics, in contrast, encourages constant testing and iteration as it doesn't require as much observation in order to come to a robust conclusion. It gives companies the agility to try new and different methods and quickly determine how effective they will be going forward.

Accuracy: The statistical methods used in predictive analytics are built to calculate the probability of their accuracy. This allows decision makers to be informed of the risks of relying on a given prediction, as opposed to historical analytics, where it is more of a subjective call as to how accurate a projection will be.

Dealing with Absent Data: Predictive analytics can be most instructive when there is insufficient historical data – or when the past is not representative of the future. For

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example, if an e-business owner is expanding into a new acquisition channel or introducing a new product category, it will not be able to rely on a historical baseline. Predictive analytics would enable it to make decisions even in the absence of past experience.

2. Aim

As an e-commerce retailer, you want to predict what your customers are looking for when they land on your site. You aim to present the most relevant recommendations to them with a higher probability of generating sales. A predictive search will determine this by analyzing their past clickthrough behavior, preferences and history in real time

3. Conclusions

Ultimately, predictive analytics can give you the ability to fully unlock the power of your data. A company that embraces predictive analytics can move past historical insights (tactics and strategies that have worked in the past) to forecast actions that will bring tremendous success in future. More importantly, the ability to extrapolate from limited data makes predictive analytics an essential constituent of a rapid-cycle testing approach. In today's rapidly-changing e-commerce landscape, the ability to experiment and optimize quickly is more important than ever, and those businesses that are able to leverage the power of predictive analytics will be at a significant advantage in the coming days.

4. Keywords

Data; Data Analytics; Predictive Analysis; Customer Segmentation; User Trends; Patterns; Forecasts; Predictions; Behavior; E-commerce

Author biography

Akshay Chhabra Akshay Chhabra has completed Bachelors of Technology in Computer Science in 2014 from Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, New Delhi, India. After graduation, he worked as Software Developer in Infosys Technologies Ltd. And Business Intelligence Analyst in EdgeVerve Systems Ltd. He is currently pursuing Master's degree in Electronic Business Technologies from University of Ottawa with a research project on Big Data Analytics and Applications in E-Commerce Systems. He has worked as a freelancer in Internet Marketing and Social Intelligence for several clothing brands for 3 years. He is also the co-founder of Kinetic Pace, a digital marketing start-up with over 7 clients in Ottawa and Toronto region.